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Views of Academics about International Students¹

Uluslararası Öğrencilere İlişkin Akademisyen Görüşleri

ABSTRACT

Globalization is an inevitable reality of the world we live in. In our changing and developing world, globalization increases the economic, cultural, social and political interaction between countries. This interaction has recently affected the field of education, which changed its direction from national to international dimension. The fact that international students are found in all levels of education today is the proof of internalisation in education. This research is qualitative research which aims to gather views of academics about the international students within the context of internationalisation of higher education. In line with this goal, interviews were made with 41 academics working in a university in the Central Anatolia Region of Turkey, and these interviews were analyzed through content analysis. According to the result of the study, Turkish higher education is preferred by international students because of some factors such as high quality education, cultural proximity, getting more freedom compared to their home countries, advantageous cities in Turkey, an opportunity to develop their self confidence, and the impact of international agreements and scholarships. Academics believe that international students have some cultural, economic, academic and social/emotional adaptation problems among which communication problems are the most notable. Regarding the challenges academics have been experiencing with international students, quality issues in education, challenges during assessment and evaluation process, problems arising from student quotas, and the problem of student grouping were identified. Some points about the process of international student admission such as Foreign Student Examination, student quotas, Turkish Language Teaching Centre, and the process of student placement should be considered and revised.

Keywords: Internationalisation, Academics, Culture, Language

ÖZET

Küreselleşme yaşadığımız dünyanın kaçınılmaz bir gerçeğidir. Gelişen ve değişen dünyamızda küreselleşme ülkeler arası ekonomik, kültürel, sosyal ve siyasal etkileşimi artırmaktadır. Bu etkileşim, son zamanlarda eğitim alanında da ulusal düzlemde uluslararası düzleme geçişin önünü açmıştır. Eğitimin tüm kademelerinde uluslararası öğrencilerin varlığı eğitimde uluslararasılaşmanın belirgin bir kanıtıdır. Yükseköğretim kurumları da değişim programları ve yapılan uluslararası anlaşmalar gereği uluslararası öğrenci sayılarını her geçen gün arttırmaktadırlar. Bu çalışma, yükseköğretimin uluslararasılaşması bağlamında yabancı uyruklu öğrencilere dair akademisyen görüşlerini almayı amaçlayan bu araştırma nitel bir araştırmadır. Bu amaçla, Türkiye'de İç Anadolu bölgesindeki bir yükseköğretim kurumunda görevli 41 akademisyen ile görüşmeler yapılmıştır. Görüşmeler içerik analizi ile çözümlenmiştir. Çalışmanın sonuçlarına göre; yabancı uyruklu öğrenciler Türk yükseköğretimini; eğitimin kaliteli olduğunu düşündükleri, kültürel bir yakınlık hissettikleri, kendi ülkelerine kıyasla Türkiye'yi daha özgür buldukları, şehirlerin avantajları olduğunu düşündükleri, özgüvenlerini geliştirmek istedikleri ve uluslararası anlaşmalar ve bursların etkisi sebepleriyle tercih etmektedirler. Akademisyenler, yabancı uyruklu öğrencilerin özellikle iletişim problemi olmak üzere kültürel, ekonomik, akademik ve sosyal/duygusal uyum problemleri yaşadıklarını düşünmektedirler. Yabancı uyruklu öğrencilerle akademisyenlerin yaşadığı problemlere dair de şu sorunlar tespit edilmiştir: eğitimde nitelik sorunu, ölçme ve değerlendirme sürecinde sorun, öğrenci kontenjanlarından kaynaklı sorunlar ve öğrencilerin gruplaşması sorunu. Yabancı uyruklu öğrencilerin alım sürecine ilişkin, katılımcı akademisyenler Yabancı Uyruklu Öğrenci Sınavı, öğrenci yerleştirme zamanlaması, öğrenci sayıları Türkçe Öğretim Merkezi ile ilgili görüşlerde bulunmuşlardır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Uluslararasılaşma, Akademisyenler, Kültür, Dil.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Globalization and Internationalization

Globalization refers to the international transfer of not only material resources but also ideas and knowledge (Tezcan, 2017; Carnoy & Rhoten, 2002). It is a phenomenon that changes and develops people in all areas of society, ranging from technology to art, economy to education, and thus shapes societies (Stromquist & Monkman, 2014). Even though globalization makes the world smaller and thus accessible to everyone, it is a concept that actually emphasises the idea of becoming one with all other societies and growing together (Çelebi, 2016). Globalization is a term considered to have both positive and negative impacts on different sectors including education. The influences of globalization on each country are unique and diverse because of a nation's individual history, traditions, culture and priorities (Knight & Wit, 1997).

Internationalisation; however, refers to the concept mostly used in education as a series of international activities such as students and teachers' mobility, international projects and partnership, and international curriculum and teaching learning process. The emphasis of internationalisation is on the relationship between and among different nations and countries. Knight (2003) defines internationalisation as "the process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions, or delivery of postsecondary education". Unlike internationalisation, globalization does not focus on the concept of nation and has a worldwide scope (Knight, 2007).

Globalization in higher education allows local resources and values to be accessible worldwide, and means a process of interaction and integration of all kinds of economic, scientific and technological developments in higher educational institutions (Altbach, 2007). Internationalisation in higher education aims to realize academic activities in more international, intercultural and global dimensions for a higher quality of education (Wit, 2012).

A crucial part of internationalisation in higher education is hosting international students. Paige (1990) defines international students as "individuals who temporarily reside in a country rather than their country of citizenship and permanent residence in order to participate in international educational exchange as students, teachers and researchers". To consider a student as international, three factors are to be paid attention to: temporary status, educational purpose and distinguishing cultural backgrounds from the host country students.

1.2. Internationalization of Higher Education in Turkey

Turkey's geopolitical position is the most important factor that facilitates the internationalization of higher education in Turkey. In addition, the abundance and diversity of higher education institutions in Turkey are other factors facilitating the internationalization of higher education in Turkey. Due to the fact that Turkey's higher education model is similar to that of Anglo-Saxon, Turkey faces fewer problems in the Bologna process, which also facilitates the internationalization of higher education in Turkey (Kondakçı, 2010).

"Department of International Relations, Department of Recognition and Equivalence and Department of Higher Education Project Development and Support" are the units that implement activities for internationalization within the Council of Higher Education. In accordance with this, the "International Relations Unit" mainly carries out activities related to relations with the European Union and international organizations, the Bologna process, relations with Middle East-Central Asian countries and scholarship students. However, the "Recognition and Equivalence Unit" operates in the fields of equivalence procedures for associate, bachelor's and master's degrees obtained from universities abroad. Along with these units, the "Project Development and Support Unit" is responsible for the fulfillment of programs featuring exchanges between higher education institutions both in Turkey and abroad (YÖK, 2023).

The internationalization of Turkish higher education started with the Turkic Republics thanks to the cultural and historical bonds among them. An analysis of the number of foreign students seeking higher education in Turkey suggests that students from Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan and the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus account for 40% of the international students in Turkey (Çetinsaya, 2014). The internationalization process of higher education in Turkey, which commenced with mutual agreements with the Turkic Republics subsequent to the division of the Soviet Union in 1991, proceeded with Europe in the 2000s.

The very first formation required in higher education took place in 1998 with the Sorbonne Declaration (YÖK, 2007), and was later legitimized with the Bologna Declaration in 1999, which was named the Bologna Process. Turkey's involvement in the Bologna Process was initiated with the Prague meeting held in 2001. The National Agency was established in 2002 and began its operations under the European Union Education

and Youth Programs (National Agency, 2007). The scope of the Bologna Declaration has been broadened and further detailed through subsequent declarations of Berlin (2003), Bergen (2005), London (2007), Leuven (2009), Budapest/Vienna (2010), Bucharest (2012) and Yerevan (2015). With the inclusion of Kazakhstan in 2010, the process extended to 47 member states and has consequently been known as the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) (Büyükgöze & Özdemir, 2016; Çetinsaya, 2014).

The 'Relations with Middle East and Central Asian Countries Unit' is another key entity in the internationalization of Turkish higher education, establishing bilateral agreements with countries in these regions to promote faculty exchanges and support 'Turkish Language Literature and Turcology' departments (Vuran-Yılmaz, 2014). Furthermore, the 'Presidency for Turks Abroad and Related Communities' contributes to the internationalization process in Turkey, notably through the provision of scholarships for international students (YTB, 2015).

Through the 'Turkey Scholarships' program, Presidency for Turks Abroad and Related Communities provides financial support to international students with monthly stipends based on their academic level, including both undergraduate and graduate students. A review of the 'Presidency for Turks Abroad and Related Communities Performance Program for 2024' reveals that the scholarships offered by Presidency for Turks Abroad and Related Communities could be categorized as follows: 'Merit Scholarship,' 'Support Scholarship,' and 'Research Scholarship' within the Short-Term Scholarship Programs; as well as scholarships for the 'Outstanding Achievement Scholarship Program,' 'Academic Support Program,' and 'International Student Internship Programs.' As well as these scholarships, Presidency for Turks Abroad and Related Communities also upholds students by covering accommodation, flight tickets, health insurance, and university fees.

Foreign Student Examination, initially introduced in 1981, was designed to ensure that foreign students were admitted to universities by means of a centralized exam process (Demirhan, 2017). In 2010, the exam was abolished, and universities were granted the autonomy to select international students based on their tailored standards (Kadıoğlu & Özer, 2015). Whereas aforementioned change led to an increase in the number of foreign students (Çetinsaya, 2014), it also brought about a decline in the quality of incoming students, instigating the reintroduction of Foreign Student Examination. Nevertheless, the exam is not the sole decisive factor, and universities preserve the autonomy and maintain the flexibility to Enforce their own admission requirements (Bulut-Şahin & Eriçok, 2023).

Another organization significantly contributing to the internationalization of Turkish higher education is the Yunus Emre Institute. Since 2009, as part of its cultural diplomacy efforts, the Institute has been actively involved in teaching Turkish as a foreign language, organizing cultural and artistic events, and promoting Turkology studies to amplify Turkey's global recognition and reputation. Higher education is also supported by the Institute through the administration of the Turkish Proficiency Exams and Foreign Student Exams for students pursuing studies (yee.org.tr).

1.3. Culture

Owing to the fact that culture is delicately connected to all aspects of human existence, including the history and development of societies, coupled with the material and spiritual interactions among individuals, it cannot be regarded separately from human beings (Berberoğlu, 1990). This interdependent relationship demonstrates that human beings are both nourished and sustained by culture, while human beings similarly, in turn, nourish, develop, and sustain culture (Nişancı, 2012).

Yalçın and Erçen (2004) suggest that culture is an essential aspect of individuals' lives, passed down to subsequent generations, and though it differs from one society to another, it also incorporates universal components across societies.

Once the material, spiritual, linguistic, and social dimensions of culture differ markedly, the process of acknowledging these differences while maintaining one's cultural identity turns out to be not only prolonged but also challenging. Accordingly, establishing a balance is imperative to navigate this intricacy.

In the contemporary world, citizens from underdeveloped and developing nations frequently seek to migrate to more developed ones such as the United States, Canada, Germany, and the United Kingdom, primarily driven by economic, health-related, and educational motivations. Each wave of migration fosters cultural exchange, thus strengthening cross-cultural engagement. Under these circumstances, Turkey has emerged as an outstanding destination for migrants, especially from countries with which it has a shared history. Turkey has attracted international students via various educational initiatives and scholarship programs, and this has

contributed to a notable increase in cultural exchange and interconnection in recent years. Nonetheless, this growing movement of people has also brought forward concepts like acculturation and cultural adaptation. When a group has an encounter with a different cultural environment, inevitably confronts challenges associated with adapting to the new cultural context (Gülнар & Balcı, 2010).

1.3.1. Cultural Adaptation

Cultural adaptation refers to the process by which individuals or small communities adjust to an environment that differs from their own cultural background, thereby the new cultural setting is able to fulfill their needs (Johnson & Sandhu, 2007).

Upon moving to a country with little or no knowledge of its culture, students seem to be compelled to fit in the educational system and campus environment of the target nation (Otrar et al., 2002). As cultural differences lessen, the so-called process of adaptation becomes more achievable. Students' ability to adapt tends to expand in settings where cultural similarities are more pronounced (Karaođlu, 2007).

1.3.2. Culture Shock

Culture shock arises when individuals face social groups that are foreign to them, about which they have little or no knowledge, and which they are being introduced to for the first time. Subsequent to culture shock, the adaptation process occurs, wherein the minority group progressively assimilates into the dominant culture. By successfully navigating this adaptation process, foreign students can overcome culture shock (Coşkunserçe, 2014)

When students relocate to another country with academic purposes, they will inevitably be exposed to cultural differences. Attributes such as the institution, city, climate, tastes, social values, beliefs, and lifestyle could vary, thus requiring the students to incrementally get adapted. This abrupt shift is widely regarded as culture shock. However, the smaller the differences, the smoother the adaptation process proves to be (Ukcisa, 2012; cited in Eynullayeva, 2020).

1.3.3. Communication and Language

The process through which individuals interact so as to be able to understand one another is referred to as communication (Öztürk, 1999). In contemporary society, communication takes place not only among individuals who share the same culture but also between individuals from different cultural backgrounds, yet interaction is more readily facilitated between individuals with similar cultural backgrounds (Genç, 2013). Therefore, culture and communication are closely related, and both mutually influence and shape each other.

The notions in our minds are delivered and shared through linguistic structures such as words (Avcı, 2012). According to Demir (2022), language functions as a tool exploited by individuals in the processes of communication in order to communicate their messages, emotions, and thoughts to the other side.

The target of the communication is to transmit messages to others through words, gestures, or movements. However, intercultural communication might be impeded, as these verbal and non-verbal facets may hold distinct meanings or be interpreted in diverse ways across cultures (Görkemli, 2019).

Andrade (2006) highlights that language proficiency has a crucial role in the social and academic adjustment processes of international students. Correspondingly, Yeh & Inose (2003) identify language proficiency as an obstacle addressed by international students in socio-academic interactions, since language forms the fundamental basis of communication.

2. METHOD

2.1. Purpose of the Research

Internationalising higher education is a crucial issue countries have been diligently working on. Like other countries in the world, Turkish higher education institutions also welcome a large number of international students, yet views of academics about these students are quite inadequate. That is why this research aims to gather the views of academics having interactions with international students in a higher education institution in Turkey, about international students.

2.2. Participants and the Research Context

The study group of this research is composed of academics working and having interactions with international students in a higher education institution in Turkey. Maximum variation sampling technique, one of the purposive sampling methods, was used to ensure maximum diversity of participants concerning

the phenomenon studied in the research. Maximum variation sampling focuses on identifying similarities between different situations owing to increased diverse criteria. This technique can be used to find similarities and common points arising from differences (Patton, 2002). To be able to achieve this aim, 41 academics with different sex, title, age and seniority, were selected from 13 different faculties of the university and 2 language schools, School of Foreign Languages and Turkish Language Teaching Centre.

2.3. Design and Procedure

This research was designed as qualitative research to gather and examine the views of academics on international students. In qualitative research, there is a direct interaction between participants and the researcher, and the answers given to the questions are greatly detailed (Yin, 2011). In this research, phenomenology was used so as to comprehend the views of academics about the phenomenon since phenomenology studies opinions, perceptions and experiences about a phenomenon (Creswell, 2018). Phenomenological studies enable researchers to obtain information about a familiar phenomenon that is indeed not known in detail, which is the reason why individuals or groups who have experienced the phenomenon are selected as data source (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018).

2.4. Data Collection Tools and Procedures

Researchers developed semi-structured interview questions to collect relevant data and determine themes and sub-themes in the data analysis process. Semi-structured questions allow participants' answers to be as detailed as possible (Cohen et al., 2018). The first draft of the semi-structured interview protocol was shaped after a review of related literature and consultation with experts in the field. This initial draft was pilot tested with four academics, and this allowed the researcher to give the final format of the semi-structured interview protocol including eight questions. Interviews were conducted face to face from March to June, and voice records were able to be obtained as all the participants gave permissions to do so. In almost 100 days, approximately 20-hour interviews were made.

2.5. Data Analysis

In this study, content analysis was used to examine data. Content analysis is a research process used to systematically study various types of data with the aim of grouping and extracting meaning (Vespestad & Clancy, 2021). The focus of this analysis is on reaching underlying meanings and messages of the content rather than the elements that can be detected with ease by conducting an in-depth examination (Yüksel, 2019). In order to carry out the content analysis, the researcher initially decoded the audio scripts and organized the textual data. The study used a coding method, an analytical approach that researchers use to retrieve important information from complex data sets. This method is mostly used in qualitative research to organize, categorize, and understand large amounts of textual data, such as content analyses and interview transcripts (Kayesa & Shung-King, 2021). Participants were coded as I 1 (Interviewee), I 2, etc.

3. FINDINGS

After the data analysis, the themes of education, cultural proximity, freedom, city, international agreements, scholarships and gaining self-confidence regarding the reasons why foreign students prefer Turkey; the themes of cultural, economic, academic, and emotional/social difficulties regarding the problems experienced by international students; the themes of assessment and evaluation, student quotas, educational quality and grouping among international students regarding the problems experienced by academics with international students; the themes of Foreign Student Examination, student placement, student numbers and Turkish Language Teaching Centre regarding the international student admission process were determined. In this section, the themes determined within the scope of the research are presented and discussed.

3.1. The Reasons Why Foreign Students Prefer Turkey

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'education' are:

— *'Unless they have the branches they are seeking for in their own countries or a field they would like to have a career in, they can choose us for that... This could be for both education and language acquisition.'* (I 1)

— *'Many of our universities are far ahead in terms of the quality of education; that's why they would love to study here.'* (I 6)

— *'Because of having higher quality education, students from other countries can come to Turkey.'* (I 21)

— *'I can especially say for the field of brain surgery that receiving training here enables international students to improve themselves. Our hospital is good in that respect. It is good in terms of education. We provide students with quality education.'* (I 41)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'cultural proximity' are:

— *'The students I have met so far are generally from Turkic Republics, Bulgaria or Greece. They are students who are connected to Turkey. Therefore, we are culturally close countries.'* (I 1)

— *'They feel closer to Turkey. There are those who prefer it due to its religion, as it is a Muslim country.'* (I 10)

— *'We have so many students from Turkic Republics. They may prefer Turkey because they think it is close to their own culture.'* (I 13)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'city' are:

— *'Considering the Middle East and Africa, the reason why students from countries that are the center of wars and chaos come here is that it is a completely safe city. They meet their security needs here.'* (I 4)

— *'City may be one of the reasons for choosing Turkey. I mean students really adapt more easily here.'* (I 23)

— *'In Turkey, lots of universities are great, the campuses are nice, and the cities are beautiful. It may also be because they think the cities they will go to are beautiful.'* (I 33)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'freedom' are:

— *'Turkey's libertarian structure, the level of this can be questioned, but when compared to some countries, it is definitely much more advanced than them. This could be why it is preferred.'* (I 32)

— *'I think they are coming here for freedom. That is to say, because Turkey is a freer country compared to the existing religious bases or political views in their countries.'* (I 35)

— *'One of the biggest reasons why Iranians prefer here is freedom.'* (I 15)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'international agreements' are:

— *'As an example, Turkey has international agreements with Turkic Republics. We prioritize them.'* (I 3)

— *'There are times we also invite most of the students through an invitation letter. This is of course provided by quota agreements among countries.'* (I 4)

— *'Programs such as student exchange have an impact on this.'* (I 6)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'scholarships' are:

— *'Most of these students, almost all of them, want to study in Turkey because they receive scholarships from the Presidency of Turks Abroad and Related Communities, under the Presidency of the Republic of Turkey.'* (I 4)

— *'There are many students coming from Africa through from the Presidency of Turks Abroad and Related Communities' scholarship. Within the scope of Erasmus, there are partner countries within K171. We also made a dual degree agreement with Azerbaijan.'* (I 20)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'gaining self-confidence' are:

— *'It could be because they want to enhance their self-confidence.'* (I 1)

— *'When students from countries with difficult living conditions and under embargo discover that there is a completely different world when going abroad, they gain self-confidence. They come with the desire to build this self-confidence.'* (I 39)

3.2. The Problems Experienced by International Students

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'cultural difficulties' are:

— *'In fact, some students have difficulties adapting Turkish language because especially those who come from Arabian geography may have problems with the alphabet, or a native speaker of English from the USA*

or a native speaker of Spanish from Venezuela may experience some difficulties while learning the sentence structure of Turkish language.' (I 6)

___ *'For instance, we have Palestinian students whose religious sensitivity was a bit higher, and I expected that, but actually they turned out to be not that strict. They are not that different from us, I mean.'* (I 7)

___ *'Most of them already come from a culture closer to ours. That is why I don't think they are experiencing such a big culture shock, but language adaptation, especially in the faculty of health sciences, is a significant problem.'* (I 18)

___ *'Everything is different; from language to food. Because they have not fully mastered the language, they have a lot of difficulty in the lessons.'* (I 38)

___ *'Apparently, a foreign student can lead to some problems in group work, which is the popular belief. Some students are at a good level, but there are also others with problems. When this happens, it probably poses a kind of prejudice for others, as well.'* (I 12)

___ *'In some countries, to illustrate, a child who has been brought up within the borders of their own traditions and customs may experience trivial culture shocks in certain social exchanges upon going to a freer country.'* (I 25)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of economic difficulties are:

___ *'If the students do not have any scholarships or their family does not have enough financial means, they may need to find a job and work there.'* (I 3)

___ *'Since what is expected from international students is to prefer a more developed country to pursue a study, they become disadvantageous in that host country.'* (I 8)

___ *'The economic conditions in the country where you are hosted as an international student influences your finances, too.'* (I 13)

___ *'Due to their limited scholarship, they need to cope financially.'* (I 25)

___ *'I think they have economic hardship. What I mean is students from Africa have financial issues. I once went to a student's house, and it was not in good condition.'* (I 40)

___ *'... I can easily notice they are having financial difficulties by looking at their clothes. They do not wear a coat even in winter.'* (I 23)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'emotional problems' are:

___ *'Students may have a feeling of loneliness owing to prejudices and if they have no friends.'* (I 3)

___ *'If the region the student goes to isn't open to foreigners, the student might not feel a social belongingness. Hence, this could cause alienation, and they may experience problems of loneliness and depression.'* (I 18)

___ *'Language incompatibility is a situation that is not approached pleasantly in our society; in contrast, it is considered to be ridiculous or ridiculed. This situation can force the student into solitude.'* (I 31)

___ *'Their interaction with other students is quite limited. They are on their own most of the time.'* (I 37)

___ *'They find the longing unbearable. For this reason, they might decide to go back.'* (I 10)

___ *'One of the challenges these students face is homesickness and feeling as if they are outsiders in the country they're in.'* (I 17)

3.3. The Problems Experienced by Academics with International Students

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'assessment and evaluation' are:

___ *'Owing to their lack of familiarity with certain assessment methods, it is necessary for them to be provided with an initial orientation. To give an example, they tend to use ballpoint pens on optical mark forms.'* (I 1)

___ *'From my viewpoint, the main issue with international students lies more in the assessment process rather than in teaching itself.'* (I 2)

__ *'They might turn up late for the exams or fail to entirely comply with the exam rules. As a result, in these cases when they miss the exams, we end up preparing make-up exams for them.'* (I 5)

__ *'We particularly struggle to understand graduate students because their accents are different from ours.'* (I 12)

__ *'Handwritten exams pose some difficulties. Their handwriting can be rather difficult to read.'* (I 13)

__ *'They tend to bring down the overall grade curve.'* (I 19)

__ *'Written expression is really challenging in terms of assessment. I also had an international thesis student at the graduate level. And again we faced similar problems with written expression. In spite of their strong speaking and comprehension skills, they struggled with structuring proper paragraphs and presenting their thesis with a coherent flow.'* (I 21)

__ *'They write in a quite unusual way, and at times I genuinely find it difficult to understand their papers during evaluation... They tend to write with little or no spacing, use ballpoint pens, make mistakes and then try to erase or scribble over them with the pen. Such things bring about problems in traditional written exams.'* (I 23)

__ *'There was a student who was repeatedly asking for word meanings during the exams. It was a bit disruptive and we were getting uncomfortable as they did it in each and every exam. Eventually, we started looking up the meaning ourselves and telling them.'* (I 25)

__ *'There were several attempts at cheating.'* (I 28)

__ *'I allocate twice the amount of standard exam duration that should normally be provided for the exam. Although these are actually 30-minute exams, I have to extend this duration since they are not proficient in the language.'* (I 31)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'student quotas' are:

__ *'It seems that a smaller number of students would improve the quality.'* (I 25)

__ *'Our department officially admits 70 students; however, the number often exceeds the quota owing to incoming international students and horizontal transfers, which reaches up to 110. This situation raises concerns regarding how to organize and group these students effectively.'* (I 34)

__ *'It would actually be more fruitful to admit well-qualified students rather than focusing merely on quantity, whereas increasing student numbers might seem to be advantageous.'* (I 8)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of 'educational quality' are:

__ *'There is a wide range of academic performance among the students, from high-achievers to low-achievers. And all of them are assigned to the same faculty members, which certainly places an extra burden on the academic advisors.'* (I 12)

__ *'The inability to attract academically well-qualified students has created a considerable amount of decline in educational quality, which could be attributed to the aforementioned student population.'* (I 15)

__ *'Due to students' inadequate mathematical competency, instructors are often prompted to provide additional instruction on foundational first-year topics, which disrupts the progression and overall flow of the course.'* (I 39)

__ *'Students are likely to be utilizing this as a gateway of transition. A significant number of the enrolled students subsequently take part in Erasmus programs to European countries or work and travel opportunities in the United States. Also, there are instances of students that leave and do not return.'* (I 32)

__ *'Thanks to the educational opportunities available in Turkey, the country might serve as a transitional spot for students targeting relocation to western destinations such as Europe or the United States.'* (I 28)

__ *'Evidently, it is seen as a facilitating bridge country by those who intend to move beyond.'* (I 15)

__ *'A great majority of international students pursue their graduate education here, yet they continue with doctoral studies in some other countries. In this respect, Turkey is typically regarded as a transitional point.'* (I 12)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of ‘grouping among international students’ are:

___ *‘Within the classroom, different student groupings have appeared. I mean they exhibit scarcely any interaction with Turkish students.’* (I 18)

___ *‘At a certain point, incoming international students often tend to self-segregate into their own subgroupings. To illustrate, if we walked around the school campus right now, we would see Turkmen students clustered together, and similarly, Kazakh students formed their own group.’* (I 32)

___ *‘Because the interaction between Turkish students and international students is usually not enough to develop a friendship, these students are in a group with other international students.’* (I 13)

___ *‘I have witnessed that international students tend to socialize within their own social clusters around the campus.’* (I 14)

3.4. The Admission Process of International Students

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of ‘Foreign Student Examination’ are:

___ *‘They say the exam is too easy. Turkish students complain about it so much as they think they strive in vain.’* (I 23)

___ *‘It would be better to revise Foreign Student Examination to turn it into an exam like our university entrance exam. This would ensure that international students would only be placed with their score of a fairer exam, not with their wish, just like our students do.’* (I 7)

___ *‘The exam is so easy that these students can be enrolled in departments where our Turkish students can be placed with a certain percentile.’* (I 27)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of ‘student placement’ are:

___ *‘I do not know how exactly these students are selected, but I do not think they are selected and placed into universities fairly, so they definitely need to be placed in our universities through fairer criteria.’* (I 30)

___ *‘The admission and placement process of these students had better be planned more carefully. Sometimes, some sudden changes or decisions are made in the middle of the term.’* (I 26)

___ *‘I heard that an international student was placed in the department of dentistry in the middle of the term during pandemic years. This student has to be accepted, but it results in lack of learning especially in such crucial departments dealing with human health.’* (I 27)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of ‘number of students’ are:

___ *‘Although we are asked about the number of the students in departments, more student quotas are provided in the end regardless of our opinions. That is why we sometimes perceive these students as extra.’* (I 26)

___ *‘I think the fewer international students means the better we engage with these students individually. For instance, if a class consisting of 100 students only has 3 international students, it is surely better for me to invite these students to my office in order to contribute academically when needed compared to 40 international students in the same class.’* (I 25)

___ *‘Despite the common perception of the student quotas, which states that international students occupy my place at university, these quotas have already been determined. This may be explained clearly.’* (I 10)

Some sample quotes of the participants regarding the theme of ‘Turkish Language Teaching Centre’ are:

‘Since there has been an accreditation problem for a while, each Turkish Language Teaching Centre conducts its own proficiency exam in Turkish. As a result of this, while one student scores B1 from the exam in one institution, another student scores C1 in another Turkish Language Teaching Centre.’ (I 10)

‘Estimate, there are 110-120 Turkish Language Teaching Centre in Turkey. They have to be accredited.’ (I 4)

‘If I have difficulties in understanding students and make them repeat what they are saying a few times, it means either the students are not competent enough in Turkish or Turkish Language Teaching Centre graduate students who are not sufficiently qualified.’ (I 31)

4. DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTIONS

According to the result of the study, international students would like to study in Turkish universities due to high quality education, cultural proximity especially in terms of language and religion, perceived freedom, advantageous cities in Turkey, increased self-confidence, international agreements and scholarships. In a similar vein, Kiranlı-Güngör & Musali (2019), found that Azerbaijani students' decisions regarding graduate studies in Turkey were affected by the bond and strong relationship between these two nations and their idea that graduate study in Turkey will improve them personally. According to Gültekin (2015) and Selimoğlu (2024), in line with the impact of the quality of education in Turkish higher education, the idea that the country is a modern one offering plenty of opportunities also plays an important role in international students' preference to pursue a university degree in Turkey. The fact that Turkey has a major role in the Islamic world is quite crucial for the students from Central Asia, Middle East and Africa. Since Turkey is a Muslim country and international students have a chance of receiving a scholarship from the Turkish government (Selimoğlu, 2024), higher education in Turkey becomes rather appealing to international students especially the ones from African countries when the life standards there are considered.

It is a must for all international students to go through adaptation process when they are in a completely different culture from theirs. In this study, it was found that international students experience numerous challenges including cultural adjustment issues resulting from prejudices and stereotypes or cultural differences in languages, beliefs, values and/or behaviours; financial limitations; emotional and social problems, and academic difficulties caused by all of these adaptation challenges. Undoubtedly, international students suffer from culture shock and struggle to adapt to the new culture they are in (Hussain & Shen, 2019). The ability to communicate is the most crucial component in enabling this adaptability. Tekin (2024) concurs with the study's findings about communication issues. According to Tekin, international students who are highly proficient in Turkish and English have higher adaptation levels than those who are not. However, international students frequently feel alone in their host countries because they struggle to overcome the language barrier in either English or Turkish, which restricts social and cultural engagement. Other research also reinforces the idea that these students experience loneliness in their host countries (Trice, 2007; Arthur, 1997). Berry et al. (1987) also claims psychological adjustment and socio-cultural adjustment processes are directly related. International students' academic performance is significantly impacted by language barriers. The parallel findings are consistent with previous research in the field (Poyrazlı & Kavanaugh, 2006; Trice, 2003; Russell et al., 2010). Andrade (2006) highlights that language barriers, and differences between educational systems and instructional strategies are the main causes of academic adaptation challenges. To improve these students' social and cultural interactions with Turkish students and to provide them the chance to practice the language they have learnt, colleges should regularly host orientation programs as well as cultural and scientific events.

Academics also experience a number of challenges in the assessment and evaluation process because of international students' language barriers. Students struggle to comprehend instructions in traditional written exams due to their poor language abilities, and often wait for clarifications during the exams. Exams last longer than normal since international students need more time to read and understand the questions compared to Turkish students. According to Iqbal & Shahid Kazi (2022), pupils struggle to comprehend the terminology in the exam; thus struggle to provide appropriate responses on written assessments. Students fail writing parts in exams because they struggle with academic language. Especially when international students are writing their master theses, consultant academics also encounter difficulties with these students due to a lack of proficiency in academic writing. This finding is supported by Eldaba & Isbell's (2018) study, which found that even after completing academic writing courses like the TOEFL and ESL, international students still struggle at American colleges. Therefore, it may be considered that academic language acquisition should be taught more by Turkish Language Teaching Centre. Alternative flexible methods in assessment and evaluation process should be preferred by academics so as to contribute to these students to face less academic problems. Assignments and presentations that these students have more time to prepare may be favored as a method of evaluation over traditional written tests. Presentations should be organized to facilitate cultural interaction and students' active participation in class thanks to cross-cultural comparisons.

Ideas regarding the process of international student admission are one of the research's findings. In particular, academics believe that Foreign Student Examination is not as challenging as the university entrance exam Turkish students take; in fact it is very easy from the point of view of academics, hence it is unfair to Turkish students. Scholars generally believe that Foreign Student Examination should be equal in complexity to the university entrance exam taken by Turkish students. Alp (2012) in his post on the website also concurs with the academics by expressing 'This exam is such an easy exam that even a child can do it with no difficulty

compared to exams such as university entrance exam in our country'. For this reason, it is strongly recommended that Foreign Student Examination must be revised urgently not to give rise to prejudice between Turkish students and international students. The study also stresses that attracting qualified students to our universities—rather than just expanding the student quotas—is more important to achieving the goal of internationalization and maintaining educational quality. Therefore, it should be considered especially during the process of determining student quotas in faculties that international students require direct counseling and support because of the challenges they may face. In the study, most of the academics agree on the problems of the Turkish Language Teaching Centre as they believe language related issues are the most fundamental ones both academics and international students encounter. The cause of these problems mainly lies beneath the accreditation of Turkish Language Teaching Centre and lack of academic language teaching (Memiş, 2021; Kara & Işır, 2021; Durmuş, 2013). That is why it is suggested to accredit Turkish Language Teaching Centre and expand the one-year preparatory program in Turkish. This is essential to prevent the language barrier which makes social and academic adaptation challenging.

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